

Adsorptive stripping voltammetric determination of cobalt in environmental samples using 2,2'-bipyridine

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A differential pulse adsorptive stripping voltammetric method has been developed for trace determination of cobalt using 2,2'-bipyridine. The base electrolyte used was 0.1 M NH₄Cl (pH 9.0). The peak current is found to increase substantially with addition of nitrite ions. A well defined peak is observed at -1.10 V. Parameters like concentration of ligand, concentration of nitrite ion, accumulation potential, accumulation time, rest period, drop size, scan rate, pulse amplitude etc. have been optimized. Under optimum conditions, the 3 σ detection limit was found to be 8.5 \times 10⁻¹⁰ M. The method is highly selective and sensitive. The method has been applied for the determination of Co^{II} in various water, ores, alloy and fish samples.

Spectrophotometry using 1-nitroso-2-naphthol¹, flame AAS², ETAAS³, ICPAES⁴ and XRF⁵ methods have been reported for determination of cobalt. Voltammetric investigations of cobalt using ligands like DMG⁶, 1,10-phenanthroline⁷, methyl thymol blue⁸, nioxime⁹, α -benzyl dioxime¹⁰ and 2-quinolinethiol¹¹ have also been reported. The detection limits in these methods vary from 10⁻⁶ to 10⁻¹⁰ M. Some of these methods suffer from low precision and accuracy at sub-ppb level. Nickel and zinc are the major interferences in these methods.

In the present work, 2,2'-bipyridine has been used as a ligand for trace level determination of Co^{II}. The complex is adsorbed on HMDE and gives a peak at -1.1 V when stripped cathodically.

Results and discussion

The pH of the solution was varied from 6.5 to 10.5 with dilute ammonia and it was observed that the peak due to electrochemical reduction of cobalt in 0.1 M NH₄Cl was not affected much with change in pH, however, the peak was found to be symmetric and well defined between pH 8.5 and 9.5. Therefore, pH of 9.0 was selected. The peak potential was found to be -1.1 V vs Ag/AgCl electrode.

The addition of nitrite ions showed a large increase in the peak current. The concentration of nitrite ions was varied from 0.1 to 1.0 M. Maximum peak height was registered at 0.6 M.

Ligand concentration was varied from 0.1 to 1.0 μ M. The peak current was found to increase with the concentra-

tion of ligand up to 0.5 μ M. After that, it remained almost constant. Ligand concentration of 1.0 μ M was selected in order to keep it in excess. Cobalt, at ppb levels does not give any peak in the absence of ligand.

Adsorptive accumulation of the complex was carried out from -0.2 to -0.8 V. A maximum peak current was obtained at -0.8 V, which was maintained for further studies.

The accumulation time was varied from 20 to 100 s. It was observed that the peak current was maximum with accumulation time of 40 s. Rest period of 15 s was found to be sufficient.

With increase in surface area of the mercury drop, a linear increase in peak current was observed and a drop size of 1.4 mm² was maintained in all the studies. Increase in the scan rate and pulse amplitude showed an increase in the

Fig. 1. Typical voltammograms of (A) blank, (B) 12.5 ng Co, (C) 25 ng Co.

Table 1. Analysis of cobalt in various samples by the experimental method

Spiked water samples		Fish samples		Ore samples	
Actual conc. (μg)	Obs. conc. (μg) ($n = 3$)	Sample	Amount of Co^{II} ($\mu\text{g/g}$)($n = 4$)	AAS method (μg)	Present method (μg)* ($n = 3$)
0.125	0.125 ± 0.002	Prawn (Nagpur)	5.68 ± 0.26	0.100	0.105 ± 0.002
0.250	0.255 ± 0.005	Marrel (Nagpur)	5.38 ± 0.20	0.105	0.113 ± 0.006
		Shilat (Mumbai))	8.47 ± 0.25	0.075	0.079 ± 0.002
		Jalva (Mumbai)	9.08 ± 0.28		

*(Avg. \pm S.D.).

peak current. Scan rate of 15 mV/s and pulse amplitude of 30 mV were selected. At higher pulse amplitude, the results were not reproducible.

Interference of other metal ions like Cr^{III} , Cr^{VI} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} was studied. It was observed that increasing the concentration of these ions individually or together from 1 to 100 times excess did not affect the symmetry or peak height. Ni^{II} was found to interfere only when present more than 10 times in excess.

The 3σ detection limit was found to be $8.5 \times 10^{-10} M$. Typical voltammograms obtained with 12.5 ng and 25.0 ng of Co^{II} in 25 ml are shown in Fig.1 and correlation coefficient of the calibration curve ($4 \times 10^{-9} - 4 \times 10^{-8} M$) was found to be 0.9997.

Applications of the method :

The above method was applied for the determination of Co^{II} in water, ores, alloy and fish samples.

Spiked water samples : 100 ml of tap water samples spiked with 0.125 and 0.250 μg of cobalt followed by 1 ml conc. HNO_3 , were evaporated to almost dryness and residue dissolved in 10 ml double-distilled water. Appropriate amounts of NH_4Cl , NaNO_2 and 2,2'-bipyridine solutions were added, pH was adjusted to 9.0 with dilute ammonia and voltammograms recorded were evaluated for concentrations. The values are listed in Table 1.

Sea water sample : A synthetic sea water sample analysed for cobalt showed an average value of $(8.43 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-9} M$ ($n = 3$) as against expected $8.5 \times 10^{-9} M$.

Fish samples : Fish samples were collected from local market in Nagpur and Mumbai and digested using acid digestion process¹². Suitable aliquots were taken and the voltammograms were recorded. The results obtained using standard addition method are shown in Table 1.

Ore samples : Three ore samples were obtained from Indian Bureau of Mines. Accurately weighed samples were digested in acids, suitable aliquots were taken and voltammograms were recorded after setting the conditions.

The amounts of cobalt found in these samples by present method and checked with AAS method are listed in Table 1.

Alloy sample : Accurately weighed high-speed steel sample (British Chemical Standards) was taken in a beaker and dissolved in 1 : 1 HNO_3 . The volume was made up to 250 ml with double-distilled water. Suitable aliquots of this solution were taken and the amount of cobalt was determined using standard addition method. Cobalt was found to be $5.72 \pm 0.09\%$ (average of 3 experiments) whereas the reported value was 5.7%.

Conclusion :

Ni^{II} and Fe^{II} are reported to form a 1 : 3 complex with 2,2'-bipyridine. In the present work it is considered that 2,2'-bipyridine forms 1 : 3 complex with cobalt. A simple rapid method has been developed for the determination of Co^{II} at trace level using this ligand. The method was found to be reproducible, reliable and accurate. The sensitivity is comparable with previously known methods^{11,13}. An important advantage of the method is that 40 s of accumulation period is sufficient to achieve the sensitivity of $8.5 \times 10^{-10} M$. The method can be applied to wide range of samples and the pretreatment of sample is simple and convenient as compared to earlier methods^{1-6,14}. Zinc does not interfere up to 100 times in excess while nickel interferes only when present 10 times in excess. Standard deviation, relative mean deviation and coefficient of variation at $8.5 \times 10^{-9} M$ were found to be 0.02, 4.1 and 4.8% respectively.

Experimental

Differential pulse adsorptive cathodic stripping voltammetric (DPAdCSV) studies were carried out using a Metrohm Polarecord E-506 serie-03 instrument working on 220 V stabilized AC mains. The experiments were performed in an air-conditioned room maintained at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ and humidity 50–60%.

The electrode assembly consisted of the hanging mer-

cury drop electrode (Kemula type) as the working electrode, Ag/AgCl (sat. KCl) electrode as reference electrode and a Pt electrode as an auxiliary electrode. Nitrogen gas was used for deaeration and micropipette (25 μ l) was used for addition of Co^{II} solution. Mercury was purified by aeration method and then distilled under reduced pressure in a mercury distillation unit.

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. Stock solutions of 1.7 mM Co^{II} and 1 mM 2,2'-bipyridine were used.

In an electrochemical cell, 0.1 M NH₄Cl and 0.6 M NaNO₂ were maintained in a total volume of 25 ml as supporting electrolyte. The pH was adjusted to 9.0 using dilute ammonia solution. To it 25 μ l of 2,2'-bipyridine solution was added, which made the concentration of ligand 1 μ M. Cobalt solution of desired concentration was added using micropipette. The solution was deaerated with nitrogen for 15 min before actual recording. In all cases, blank recording was performed and necessary corrections were made in the calculations.

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